

check. Each test entry was planted in two 2-m rows, spaced at 20- × 15-cm. Plants were inoculated at tillering stage with the ShB pathogen multiplied on rice stem pieces. Disease reactions were judged by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale.

Disease pressure was high (location severity index [LSI] = 7.22) for B1 and moderate (LSI = 4.60) for ShB.

CR280-5, JR49, and MGL 14 were highly resistant to ShB and 139 entries showed resistant or moderately resistant reactions. RNR788 11, WGL 26420, and

RGL 1746 were highly resistant to B1 and 39 entries had resistant to moderately resistant reactions. Although all the six lines with highly resistant reactions to one disease were susceptible to the other disease, 14 entries resistant to both diseases were identified (see table). □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Japonica cultivars are more susceptible to brown planthopper biotype 1 than Tongil hybrids

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Susceptibility of Tongil lines (japonica/indica) with no genes for resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) was studied using a seedling bulk test. Four japonica and 4 Tongil lines that are recommended to farmers in Korea were alternately planted in 15-cm-long rows in plastic boxes with 2 replications. Cultivar reaction to BPH biotype 1 was recorded at 7, 9, 11, and 13 days after infestation (DI) using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

Seedling reactions of selected rice cultivars to brown planthopper biotype 1.

Rice type	Variety	Damage rating ^a at given days after infestation			
		7d	9d	11 d	13 d
Tongil (japonica/ indica)	Milyang 23	R	R	MR	M
	Seogwangbyeon	R	R	MR	MS
	Pungsanbyeon	R	R	MR	MS
Japonica	Jinjubyon	MR	M	S	S
	Dongjinbyeon	M	MS	S	S
	Samnambyeon	M	MS	S	S
	Sangpungbyeon	M	MS	S	S
	Cheongcheongbyeon (R check)	R	R	R	R

^aBased on seedling bulk test: R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, M = moderate, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

Japonica varieties Jinjubyon, Dongjinbyeon, Samnambyeon, and Sangpungbyeon were susceptible to BPH at 11 DI. Tongil lines Milyang 23, Seogwangbyeon, and Pungsanbyeon were moderately resis-

tant to BPH at 11 DI (see table). Among rice cultivars with no BPH resistance genes, japonica cultivars at seedling stage were much more susceptible to BPH than Tongil lines. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Rice tolerance for coastal salinity

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Rice varieties were screened in rainfed fields for coastal soil salinity tolerance during kharif (Jun-Nov) 1980, 1981, and 1982 at CSSRI. Trials were in a randomized block design with three replications. Soil pH was 7.0 and soil salinity (ECe) ranged from 6.3 to 11.5 in 1980, 6.3 to 8.3 in 1981, and 9.4 to 16.9 mmho/cm in

1982 at different crop growth stages. One-hundred and sixty-three varieties or lines were compared to local checks CSRI and Nonasail (Sel), using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale. Plant survival at maturity also was recorded (see table).

In 1980 Nonasail (Sel) scored best at all stages. The lines IR4432-28-5 and IR2863-35-3-3 also were promising. In 1981 10 varieties or lines scored better than the resistant check at vegetative stage. Among them, IR9884-54-3 and M152 were the most tolerant. Although IR42 had 100% survival, it had poorer growth than IR36. Lines that performed

as well as the local check CSRI were IR4432-28-5, Nonasail (Sel), IR10198-66-2, and IR2307-247-2-2-3. IR4432-28-5, Nonasail (Sel), IR10198-66-2, and CSRI exhibited more tolerance at ripening stage than at vegetative stage. IR9852-19-2 and IR13426-19-2 had better tolerance at ripening stage.

Salinity was highest in 1982 and most varieties had high mortality and poor growth. However, M152, M242, PNL 28-23, and Nonasail (Sel) had 50% survival and performed best. Tests showed that there are three levels of salt tolerance: tolerance at all growth stages, tolerance at vegetative stage, and tol-

erance at ripening stage. Nonasail (Sel), CSR6, CSRI, M152 in that order, had tolerance at all growth stages. IR4432-28-5 and IR13426-19-2 performed well and IR9884-54-3 appeared suitable for medium saline soils. □

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Consequences of small farm mechanization

Investigaciones en arroz en los años 1980: resumen de los informes de la conferencia internacional de investigaciones en arroz del año 1982

Map series of Bangladesh: rice area planted by season, rice area planted by culture type, farm size distribution, and base map.

Field scores and survival of some promising varieties or lines in screening for tolerance for coastal salinity.

Variety or line	Plant survival at maturity (%)				Tolerance score ^a							
					Vegetative				Maturity			
	1980	1981	1982	Av	1980	1981	1982	Av	1980	1981	1982	Av
IR36	56	99	16	57	8	4	8	7	6	6	9	7
IR42	48	100	12	53	8	6	8	7	7	5	8	7
IR4432-28-5	79	98	21	66	6	4	8	6	5	4	8	6
IR9852-19-2	57	98	30	61	8	6	6	6	7	4	8	6
IR9884-54-3	73	99	19	64	7	4	7	6	6	4	8	6
IR9975-5-1	62	69	11	47	7	6	7	7	6	6	8	7
M152	34	91	74	66	8	4	3	5	7	4	4	5
M242	37	63	64	55	8	4	5	6	7	5	6	6
Nonasail (Sel)	92	87	61	80	4	4	4	4	4	4	6	4
PNL 11-2	60	9	24	31	7	4	7	6	6	7	6	6
PNL 28-23	70	61	53	61	6	6	8	6	7	6	8	7
IR10198-66-2	70	93	15	59	7	4	8	6	7	4	8	6
IR10206-29-2	59	84	22	55	8	6	8	7	7	5	8	7
IR13426-19-2	58	83	—	71	7	5	—	6	7	4	—	5
IR2307-247-2-2-3	55	99	19	58	8	4	8	6	6	5	8	6
IR2863-35-3-3	79	96	5	60	6	6	9	7	5	5	9	6
Pokkali	7	60	4	24	8	9	9	8	6	7	8	7
M-1-48	59	2	—	30	8	9	—	9	9	9	—	9
CSRI		97	37	67	—	4	6	5	—	3	5	4

^a1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 1-9: 1 = growth and tillering nearly normal; 9 = almost all plants dead or dying.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Performance of some promising varieties in floating-rice areas of Cuu Long Delta

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Deepwater rice is grown on about 0.5 million ha on the Cuu Long (Mekong) Delta. Most is grown in An Giang, Dong Thap, Kien Giang, Hau Giang, and Long An Provinces. There is little information on agronomic characteristics and yield of popular local varieties.

We compared local varieties Nang Tay Dum, Nang Tay Lon, Nang Chet Cut, Ba Bong, Sa Mo Chum, Cu La, and introduced varieties Leb Mue Nahng 111, BKNFR76031-1-13-1, BKNFR76047-4-3-1, and RD19 at An Giang and Hau Giang (see table).

In Jun 1982 1-month-old seedlings were transplanted in 25- × 25-cm spacing at 1 seedling/hill. Maximum water depth

Grain yield and plant characters of some photoperiod-sensitive rices in floating-rice areas of Cuu Long (Mekong) Delta, S. R. Vietnam, 1982.

Variety	Date of heading	Height (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Field grains/panicle	Unfilled grains %	1000-grain weight (g)	Yield ^d (t/ha)	
Local				<i>An Giang</i>				
Ba Bong	07 Dec	260	89	146	12.3	32.2	3.0	def
Cu La	20 Nov	247	108	151	16.3	23.9	3.3	cd
Nang Chet Cut	17 Nov	250	92	151	18.2	24.8	2.9	ef
Nang Tay Dum	23 Nov	254	89	195	18.4	22.8	3.6	a
Nang Tay Lon	23 Nov	255	83	133	15.9	29.7	3.6	ab
Sa Mo Chum	25 Nov	237	103	165	14.3	22.5	3.4	abc
<i>Introduced^b</i>								
BKNFR76031-1-13-1	23 Nov	228	92	82	30.9	34.4	2.5	g
BKNFR76047-4-3-1	01 Dec	210	69	98	27.9	28.7	2.2	g
Leb Mue Nahng 111	22 Nov	255	88	116	22.7	31.8	3.0	def
RD19	05 Dec	208	117	62	25.3	30.7	3.1	cde
Local				<i>Hau Giang</i>				
Ba Bong	01 Dec	212	69	121	18.0	33.3	3.7	a
Cu La	19 Nov	231	88	84	30.7	24.3	2.5	b
Nang Chet Cut	15 Nov	248	75	99	20.0	24.6	2.6	b
Nang Tay Dum	30 Nov	244	65	158	20.5	23.3	2.7	b
Nang Tay Lon	20 Nov	258	71	102	20.2	28.3	2.5	b
<i>Introduced^b</i>								
BKNFR76031-1-13-1	21 Nov	245	76	96	24.1	34.9	2.5	b
Leb Mue Nahng 111	20 Nov	256	62	103	23.9	32.0	2.4	b
Pin Gaew 56	15 Dec	298	84	127	19.2	30.8	3.4	a

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. ^bFrom Thailand.